

Political aspects on economic development: a kaleckian-structuralist perspective¹

Julia Juárez García²; Felipe Cruz Díaz³

Abstract

This article reconsiders economic development from a Kaleckian perspective, highlighting how supply-side structural constraints—shaped by political factors affecting income distribution—undermine aggregate demand in developing economies. While Kalecki is known for linking income distribution to effective demand, this study emphasizes that persistent underdevelopment must be understood through the political economy interactions among public, private, and external sectors. By engaging Kalecki with Latin American structuralism, the article offers a theoretical reassessment of development, critiquing early Anglo-Saxon structuralist approaches for neglecting the political roots of structural bottlenecks. The proposed Kaleckian–Structuralist framework integrates political economy and structural dynamics as core components for analyzing development through its political dimension.

Keywords: Kaleckian political economy; economic development; income distribution; structural constraints; Latin American structuralism.

JEL Classification: B31; O11; P16.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18054646.

¹ This work was supported by the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México Postdoctoral Program.

² Postdoctoral researcher at National Autonomous University of Mexico, Faculty of Superior Studies Acatlan; email: Julia.juarez.garcia@comunidad.unam.mx

³ Full professor at National Autonomous University of Mexico National Autonomous University of Mexico, Faculty of Superior Studies Acatlan; fel_economia@comunidad.unam.mx

Introduction

One of the most remarkable aspects of Michal Kalecki's legacy is the breadth of his work, spanning rigorous economic modeling and incisive political economy analysis. Largely self-taught, he became one of the most original and prolific economists of his generation. His approach transcended conventional boundaries, leaving a lasting impact on both theoretical and applied economics, and ensuring his continued relevance in contemporary analyses of power and political economy (Rochon, 2020, p. 487).

Rather than proposing a rigid theoretical model, Kalecki's enduring relevance lies in his method—one that prioritizes class structure, income distribution, and power configurations as central to understanding economic policy. This approach continues to inspire those analyses that seek to explain structural limitations through political economy frameworks (Ghosh, 2005, p. 12).

His work was profoundly shaped by a commitment to social justice, and throughout his career, he endeavored to connect theory with real-world experience—a stance aligned with the principles of critical realism, as noted by Jefferson and King (2011, p. 957). His formulation of the principle of effective demand, which preceded that of Keynes, is intrinsically tied to political economy. Kalecki's focus on developing economies reveals a deep awareness of the political pressures and institutional constraints shaping the development process (Sachs, 1999, p.55).

Although his body of work explicitly devoted to what is now termed “economic development” is relatively limited, its influence is nevertheless significant. His contributions in this area are typically concise, often articulated through short articles that distill key principles without extensive theoretical elaboration. While he may not fit the traditional mold of a development theorist—given his role as a policy consultant and the absence of a systematic, formalized body of work—his succinct contributions mark him as a pioneering thinker, offering ideas ahead of his time.⁴

This article revisits three of Kalecki's key writings (1943, 1955, 1967), building on his foundational contributions to the theory of effective demand—a central theme in his work since the 1930s. It asks: *What can the Kaleckian theory of development contribute to understanding the political aspects of development within a structuralist framework?*

Our hypothesis is that these texts offer valuable insights into Kalecki's approach to political economy and its implications for economic development. In this context, the article seeks to integrate Kalecki's heterodox thought with the critical foundations of

⁴ Kalecki's dedication to academic collaboration on economic development is reflected in three main initiatives: In 1958, he launched a seminar on underdeveloped economies, held regularly for nearly a decade. In 1961, he helped establish a Research Centre on underdeveloped economies at Warsaw University, where he chaired the Scientific Board. He also contributed to the Higher Course in National Economic Planning, mentoring economists from Latin America, Africa, and Asia, supervising several doctoral theses (Sachs, 1977, p. 48).

Latin American structuralism, offering a complementary perspective that helps illuminate the political constraints shaping development processes.

The study aims to contribute in two ways: first, by proposing a framework that allows for alternative policy prioritization under binding supply constraints and politically contentious contexts—contrasting with standard post-Keynesian approaches; and second, by incorporating political dimensions into Kalecki’s dual-sector model, drawing on insights from the primary manuscripts discussed above.

First, we examine Kalecki’s canonical model, which addresses the key challenge of financing economic development. Unlike mid-20th-century supply-side approaches, his demand-driven framework provides a perspective capable of overcoming the limitations of traditional models. We then explore the political dimensions of Kalecki’s theory, focusing on his 1967 analysis of what he defined as “*intermediate regimes*” that emerged during the process of decolonization. This work illustrates how the distribution of power among public, private, and external actors’ shapes development outcomes, highlighting how these power relations can both enable and constrain progress.

By integrating the demand-driven model with a political economy perspective, the article highlights two fundamental insights. First, structural economic barriers hinder the effective implementation of demand-led growth strategies. Second, political constraints—often aligned with the interests of dominant groups—exacerbate these barriers, creating additional obstacles to sustained development.

This paper is structured into four sections, following this introduction. The first section explores the role of investment in both developed and developing economies, highlighting how Kalecki’s structuralist perspective diverges from early Anglo-Saxon structuralism and aligns more closely with key conclusions of Latin American structuralism. The second section revisits the political dimension of his foundational work, particularly focusing on the political cycle that accompanies developed capitalism. These findings are then analyzed in the third section, where the political aspects of development are critically reflected upon. The paper concludes in the fourth section, synthesizing the insights gained and drawing connections between Latin American structuralism and Kalecki’s framework, ultimately proposing the development of a “Kaleckian structuralism”.

1. A matter of investment: Financing economic development

If a Kaleckian theory of economic development exists, its foundation lies in a series of lectures delivered at the *Centro de Estudios Monetarios Latinoamericanos* (CEMLA) in Mexico City in 1953, later published as *The Problem of Financing Economic Development*. Despite its significance, the lack of formalization limited the reach of Kalecki’s model, leaving several key aspects underexplored. For this reason, revisiting and attempting to formalize this contribution has become a challenge taken up by scholars, as illustrated by the work of Fitzgerald (1988, p. 33, 1990, p. 184) and others.

First, it is important to clarify that in this context, the concept of financing is not limited to monetary considerations. From the outset of his dissertation, financing is framed as the allocation of resources within the productive structure. Within this framework, there are no strict financial constraints on investment in the traditional sense; the primary concern is whether increased investment could generate inflationary pressures under the structural limitations of the economy.

For instance, higher investment in an environment with an inelastic food supply could reduce real wages and trigger an inflationary wage–price spiral; for a discussion of the implications and transmission mechanisms, see Juárez and Moreno-Brid (2024, p. 6). This, in fact, represents the point of connection between Kalecki and Latin American structuralism, as illustrated by the analysis of inflation in Chile discussed by Sunkel (1996). More recently, similar mechanisms of inflationary pressure driven by sectoral supply inelasticities—including those related to primary resources—have also been observed in the supply shocks triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic, as shown by Bañbura et al. (2023, p. 4) and Setterfield (2023, p. 587).

At the heart of the issue is a distributive dilemma: determining which social groups will absorb the costs of expanding capital accumulation, often through reduced consumption. This moves the discussion beyond technical or economic efficiency, situating investment decisions within the political sphere. These decisions ultimately reflect broader power relations and the underlying social structure of the economy (Ghosh, 2005, p. 3).

The starting point for understanding Kalecki's conception of development and the relation with investment is rooted in a fundamental assertion: the cause of unemployment in developing economies differs from that in developed capitalist economies. While in the latter, unemployment results from inadequate effective demand due to cyclical fluctuations, in contrast, developing economies face a more structural issue—namely, a shortage of capital equipment. While effective demand deficiencies may occasionally play a role, they are not seen as the primary cause. This distinction highlights the supply-side constraints that characterize the challenges of development in developing economies (López and Assous, 2010, p. 174).

Given this scenario, developing economies face a chronic need for investment that can overcome the capital shortage. However, as suggested by Kalecki (1955, p. 7), there are three key obstacles to achieving such levels of investment. Each of these obstacles is linked to a component of effective demand, pointing to the complex interrelation between investment, demand, and economic growth in these contexts.

Table 1. Investment constraints for development		
$I = I_p + I_G$	Investment	Insufficient private investment
$X_n = (X_{I,C} - M_{I,C})$	Foreign Trade	Underdeveloped investment goods industries
$C_T = C_A + C_I = \theta C + (1 - \theta)C$	Consumption	Inflationary pressure on necessities
Source: Own elaboration based on Kalecki (1955)		

Table 1 presents a synthesis of the structural obstacles identified by Kalecki (1955, p. 8) that hinder underdeveloped economies from achieving the investment levels necessary to meet their chronic need to strengthen installed productive capacity. First, it highlights that private investment may be insufficient, a condition that could, under certain circumstances, be compensated by public investment. Second, it considers the scenario of a shortage of capital goods, which could be addressed through foreign trade, assuming an open economy.

However, under the assumption of a closed economy ($X_n = 0$) and the absence of government intervention ($I_G = 0$), the central issue shifts toward the sphere of consumption. In this context, Table 1 shows how pressures on agricultural production affect food demand (θ), which in turn proportionally impacts industrial consumption ($1 - \theta$). These dynamics illustrate the structural constraints that limit both the expansion of aggregate demand and the capacity to sustain long-term productive accumulation, ultimately shaping a key barrier to development.

In developing economies, the structural duality is evident, with a demand-driven industrial sector and a supply-constrained agricultural sector. The industrial sector faces a chronic need for investment to expand its installed capacity and absorb surplus labor, while the agricultural sector struggles to increase output at the same pace due to its inherent rigidity and limited ability to respond to rising demand.

According to Kalecki, this asymmetry is not merely a short-term issue but reflects deep structural constraints rooted in the semi-feudal organization of agriculture. In such conditions, food prices respond sharply to demand fluctuations, generating inflationary pressures that hinder development. Market forces alone cannot correct these imbalances; a deliberate public strategy is required to expand agricultural capacity and remove the structural barriers preventing effective demand from driving growth.

A core element of Kalecki's argument is the distributive dimension, where economic and social constraints intersect. He argues that national income growth depends on expanding basic necessities, yet institutional barriers limit agricultural

development. As agricultural output cannot grow indefinitely without causing inflation, economic expansion must align with productive capacity. Kalecki (1976, p. 98) further emphasizes that development should follow principles of social justice—avoiding inflation in essential goods and taxes on low-income groups—since inflation from limited supply disproportionately erodes the purchasing power of the most vulnerable. In this sense, inflationary pressures are not only economic but inherently political, as they produce an unequal redistribution of income that reinforces inequality and fuels social and political instability, ultimately constraining the development process.

Therefore, Kalecki’s approach underscores the need for deliberate public policies that address not only economic challenges but also the distributive power dynamics that shape the course of development. In developing economies, it is crucial that development policies take into account both economic and political aspects of income redistribution to prevent growth from reinforcing social inequalities and to ensure that development is inclusive and sustainable.

More broadly, Kalecki (1955, p. 4, 1976, p. 98) emphasizes that meaningful development requires profound social transformations, particularly a shift in power from landowners to peasants. Yet, he recognizes that such structural changes are inherently conflictual, often encountering resistance that prevents their peaceful implementation.

1.2. Early structuralism of dual perspective

In the post–World War II context, Latin American governments pursued policies aimed at promoting industrialization and accelerating economic growth. Development was largely understood as a process of factor accumulation—particularly capital accumulation—where industrial expansion was viewed as the primary means to overcome poverty and “underdevelopment” (Perez Caldentey & Vernengo, 2007, p.1).

Kalecki’s perspective, however, offers a broader and more integrated understanding of development. Rather than equating progress solely with industrial growth, he highlights the strategic importance of the agricultural sector—not merely as a source of labor or surplus, but as an essential pillar of a balanced and inclusive development strategy. By emphasizing the political economy of structural transformation and the centrality of income distribution, Kalecki redefines the development debate, underscoring that sustainable growth depends on addressing both economic and social asymmetries within the productive structure.

Kalecki’s pioneering analytical perspective is original in the priorities it sets for understanding development—priorities that differ markedly from those of contemporaries such as Nurkse (1955) and Lewis (1954). This divergence is not merely methodological but rooted in a central concern with the relationship between income distribution and economic growth. In Kalecki’s view, development is not a purely technical process of capital accumulation or labor absorption; it is shaped by social and political dynamics. This perspective challenges mainstream conceptions of

industrialization, which often treat structural transformation as a spontaneous outcome of market forces.

As highlighted by López and Assous (2010, p. 178), the implications of industrialization under the dual-sector model formulated by Lewis (1954, p. 139) contrast sharply with the analytical approach considered here. Lewis's model assumes that all profits are reinvested and that an increasing share of profits in national income will foster capital accumulation, stimulate output growth, and gradually absorb surplus labor. In general terms, Lewis emphasizes supply-side differences and the transition toward industrial modernization, ultimately leading to a unified capitalist sector driven by profits.

In contrast, Kalecki's framework underscores the structural constraints associated with aggregate demand and income distribution. Unlike Lewis, Kalecki assigns a central role to the agricultural sector, both as a supplier of food and as a source of demand for industrial goods. This perspective leads to a vision of development rooted in a balanced relationship between agriculture and industry, where growth is not automatic but contingent upon the dynamics of effective demand and distributive relations (Juárez, 2025, p. 3).

These features are central to his model, which considers the principle of aggregate demand to be fundamental. However, in developing economies, structural constraints often prevent this principle from operating effectively, thereby limiting the potential development.

Moreover, while Lewis contends that a decline in the rural poor's standard of living can enhance industrial profits by reducing urban wages, he neglects the potential adverse effects on aggregate demand—particularly through diminished consumption of industrial goods by the peasantry. Kalecki, by contrast, stresses that increases in the profit share—whether through wage compression or greater monopoly power—do not guarantee higher absolute profits unless accompanied by a simultaneous rise in capitalist consumption or investment (Lopez and Assous, 2010, p. 178).

Nevertheless, both models converge on one essential point: developing economies face a chronic shortage of capital that impedes the full absorption of their labor force. Where they differ is in the mechanisms proposed to overcome this constraint. Lewis relies on reinvested profits and labor reallocation, assuming that growth will be driven by internal accumulation within the capitalist sector. Kalecki, on the other hand, highlights the political economy of investment decisions and the demand-side bottlenecks that limit accumulation, thus requiring structural reforms to ensure sustained and inclusive development.

1.3. Latin American structuralism scheme

The field of economic development emerged in the aftermath of decolonization, amid growing concern over the structural challenges facing newly independent nations.

Although shaped by diverse historical and ideological forces, its consolidation was notably influenced by the Keynesian critique of neoclassical economics, which emphasized the limitations of market self-regulation and the need for state intervention. The evident shortcomings of spontaneous industrialization further reinforced the argument for an active role of the state in fostering structural transformation (Perez Caldentey and Vernengo, 2007, p. 2).

In this intellectual climate, Latin American structuralism offered a distinctive framework by introducing the center–periphery paradigm, which sought to explain the enduring asymmetries within the global economic order. Rather than treating economies in isolation, it conceptualized developed and developing countries as interconnected yet hierarchically positioned components of a single world system. This perspective enabled a more nuanced analysis of growth and income distribution in peripheral economies by combining an evolutionary understanding of technological change with Keynesian insights on demand in open economies (Porcile, 2021, p.51).

Furthermore, by grounding its analysis in historical processes, Latin American structuralism shed light on the interplay between global dynamics and domestic constraints—an insight that remains highly relevant. In this regard, Sánchez-Ancochea (2007, p. 215) highlights two limitations in early Anglo-Saxon structuralist thought: its insufficient attention to the systemic links between center and periphery, and its overestimation of the state's capacity to overcome structural barriers, often neglecting the institutional and political constraints that undermine effective intervention.

Latin American structuralism, rooted in the work of Raúl Prebisch, is grounded in a historical analysis of capitalist development that highlights the structural asymmetries between center and periphery economies. According to Bielschowsky (1998, p.4), this approach is based on four analytical pillars: the center–periphery dichotomy, the analysis of Latin America's insertion into the global economy, the study of domestic determinants of growth and technological progress, and the evaluation of state intervention. ECLAC's theory of underdevelopment posits that capital accumulation and the diffusion of technical progress occurred unevenly across countries, leading to persistent structural disparities.

A key connection between the Kaleckian perspective and Latin American structuralism lies in the theory of inflation. Structuralists in Latin America emphasized the role of external disequilibrium as a central factor in triggering inflation, particularly focusing on the structural disequilibria between the demand and supply of specific sectors. This analysis drew heavily from Kalecki's framework. One notable disequilibrium identified was the mismatch between the rapid growth of demand and the slower growth of agricultural supply. Another significant disequilibrium emerged from the limited growth in import capacity compared to the rising demand for foreign exchange (Sanchez-Ancochea, 2007, p. 210).

This integration of ideas from the principle of effective demand, as articulated by Keynes and Kalecki, owes much to the influence of Celso Furtado on Latin American structuralism. Furtado played a crucial role in embedding a political economy of development within the structuralist approach. His work effectively merged historical inductive methods with logical deductive reasoning, creating a robust tool for economic development theory (Bresser-Pereira, 2007, p.20). Furtado's engagement with the post-Keynesian theory of the Cambridge School further sharpened his critique of neoclassical economics, particularly with regard to the interplay between income distribution, demand, and capital accumulation (Cypher, 2014, p.16; Orsolin-Teixeira et al., 2023, p. 1363; Guizzo et al., 2024, p. 339).

In addition to its structural theory of inflation, one of the central contributions of ECLAC's structuralism is the concept of structural heterogeneity. This notion stems from the recognition that developed and peripheral economies are shaped by fundamentally different productive and technological structures. In advanced economies, technological progress tends to diffuse broadly across sectors, fostering diversification and relatively balanced growth.

In contrast, peripheral economies are characterized by technological dependence and a historical specialization in the export of primary goods—sectors that are more likely to absorb innovation—while large portions of the economy remain stagnant, operating with traditional, low-productivity techniques (Porcile, 2021, p.57). This dynamic leads to two defining features: specialization and heterogeneity. The latter, akin to a form of productive duality, refers to the coexistence of a dynamic, export-oriented sector alongside vast segments of low-productivity activities, particularly in agriculture and informal services.

Such an imbalance resonates closely with Kalecki's theoretical concerns, particularly his emphasis on income distribution as a determinant of effective demand. Kalecki did not view development merely as a technical process of capital accumulation, but as one deeply embedded in social and political structures, where class relations and the distribution of income shape the trajectory of growth.

In contrast to development strategies focused solely on the expansion of the industrial or capitalist sector, Kalecki advanced a political economy perspective that stressed the importance of equitable growth. His model underscored the need to strengthen the non-capitalist sectors—especially agriculture and rural areas—as a means to expand internal demand and achieve a more balanced path of structural change.

2. Political aspects on developed capitalism

Throughout his work, Kalecki consistently emphasized the relationship between economics and politics, viewing the latter as a reflection of persistent class conflict. His 1943 article *Political Aspects of Full Employment* stands as the cornerstone of his political analysis, anticipating the systemic limits to sustained expansionary fiscal policies. Although initially overlooked, the article gained prominence in the 1970s,

particularly among leftist scholars, for its critical perspective on the political barriers to full employment (Sawyer, 2023, p. 1109).

Kalecki argued that capitalist economies are governed by effective demand, making them structurally demand-constrained. Unlike supply-constrained socialist systems, they frequently face insufficient aggregate demand, resulting in persistent underutilization of resources and involuntary unemployment. Investment spending, he emphasized, is the primary driver of economic fluctuations and the central engine of the business cycle. When demand fails to absorb the available labor, full employment remains unattainable—a structural feature that explains persistent unemployment even without external shocks or restrictive policies (Sawyer, 2023, p. 1110). Achieving full employment thus requires both adequate productive capacity and sustained effective demand.

Yet, the pursuit of full employment is not purely economic; it also poses significant political challenges. Historically, capitalism has not sustained long periods of full employment, as doing so tends to bring about profound social and political changes. A comprehensive review of the empirical evidence on this debate would require an extensive discussion of one of the most scrutinized issues: state intervention in the economy aimed at achieving full employment. Nonetheless, a theoretical overview can be found in Arndt (1994, p. 2) and, more extensively, in Marsh et al. (2017, p. 488). Resistance to maintaining full employment often stems from the transformations it triggers and from opposition to increased government intervention (Sawyer, 1985, p. 125).

2.2. The political constraints of full employment

As we already mentioned, for Kalecki, the inability to sustain full employment long-term arises not from economic limits but from political constraints. Unlike other approaches, he viewed full employment as economically feasible yet obstructed by class pressures. In line with Keynes, he argued that full employment is achievable in the short term and, economically, could be maintained over time—introducing a long-term dimension often absent in traditional Keynesian analysis (Arestis and Skuse, 2003, p. 27).

Building on this, Kalecki (1944, p. 39) identified at least three methods of achieving and maintaining full employment in a capitalist society operating in a closed economy. Each of these methods is consistent with the logic of the principle of effective demand and its key components (see Table 2).

Table 2. Methods for achieving Full Employment			
Effective Demand	$D = C + I + G$		
Actor	Workers	Capitalist	Government
Component	Consumption	Private Investment	Public investment (deficit spending)
Method	Income redistribution for higher to lower income classes	Through interest rate, less income tax or measures towards assisting private investment	Public spending financed by borrowing
Source: Own elaboration based on Kalecki (1944)			

Although these mechanisms theoretically make full employment attainable without triggering inflation or reducing profits, their implementation highlights the political challenges embedded in capitalist economies. First, he observed that pursuing full employment through redistribution—via taxation or profit squeeze—offers a more equitable outcome than relying solely on deficit-financed public spending. However, the inherently redistributive nature of this approach makes it prone to political resistance. Consequently, he highlighted the essential role of government intervention in mediating the power relations between workers and capitalists, thereby enhancing the feasibility of sustained full employment (Sawyer, 1985, p. 129).

Second, stimulating private investment alone is insufficient. While investment provides the capital goods necessary for production, it cannot absorb the entire labor force, and its effectiveness is highly sensitive to business sentiment, which can fluctuate due to political uncertainty or economic pessimism. As the most volatile component of aggregate demand, private investment alone is too unstable to secure full employment.

Finally, Kalecki (1944, p. 140) emphasized the indispensable role of government intervention in filling the demand gap left by the private sector. Strategic public spending—on infrastructure, education, healthcare, or through measures such as family allowances, tax reductions, or subsidies for essential goods—can strengthen aggregate demand and sustain economic activity over time.

He further noted that, when government expenditure is carefully calibrated to meet the level of demand required for full employment, inflationary pressures remain minimal. Financing this spending through public debt, rather than higher taxes, avoids crowding out private investment and consumption. In this way, public expenditure supplements insufficient private demand, facilitating full employment without generating significant inflation.

Moreover, sustaining full employment through state intervention is technically feasible. Higher production and employment benefit both workers and entrepreneurs, as profits tend to rise alongside wages. These policies can be structured to avoid tax increases that might erode business profits, thereby balancing economic efficiency with political acceptability.

Yet, the challenge extends beyond economics to the realm of power relations. Kalecki emphasizes that while capitalists may welcome a recovery during natural recessions, they often resist the “synthetic boom” that the state can create through deliberate public spending, revealing the inherent political tensions in achieving sustained full employment.

However, the challenge is inherently political. Kalecki notes that while capitalists may welcome recoveries during ordinary recessions, they often resist the “synthetic boom” generated by deliberate public spending. Sustained full employment reduces capital’s control over labor, empowering workers, increasing their bargaining strength, and limiting their acceptance of unfavorable conditions. In this sense, the conflict is not merely economic but a fundamental struggle over power: full employment undermines the disciplinary effect of unemployment, challenging the dominance of capital.

This resistance is not a mere technical oversight; it reflects deeper structural interests. “Tolerable” levels of unemployment serve a purpose within the capitalist system, maintaining labor discipline and curbing wage pressures, as Kalecki cautions (Rowthorn, 1999). From this perspective, full employment not only improves the living conditions of the working population, but it also has the potential to foster a more profound transformation of the economic order by weakening capital’s control over labor—a possibility some have interpreted as a potential transition toward socialism (Toporowski, 2023, p. 226).

The above can be expressed through the following three reasons behind the opposition of “industrial leaders” to full employment achieved through government spending:

1. Interference in the problem of employment
2. the dislike of Government intervention (public investment and subsidizing consumption);
3. Maintenance of full employment.

First, the argument against government intervention in employment is rooted in the fear that political power may shift from the private sector to the state. Capitalists are concerned that state-led activity, or a move toward socialism, could replace private capitalism.

This concern is framed by orthodox economic thinking, which emphasizes market freedoms and the need to maintain a “state of confidence.” From this

perspective, the government should adopt a passive role, simply ensuring that markets function without interference. If confidence is undermined, they argue, investment, output, and employment will decline.

However, when the state uses public spending to sustain demand and guarantee full employment, this balance of power shifts. The threat by capitalists to withhold investment becomes less effective. In such a scenario, investment loses its power to control employment levels. The willingness of the state to intervene weakens the influence of private capital over macroeconomic outcomes.

Second, the aversion to government spending—particularly on public investment and the subsidization of mass consumption—is closely related to the previous point. As Kalecki argued, there would be pressure to limit public investment to areas that do not compete directly with private enterprise, such as hospitals, schools, and highways.

Moreover, Kalecki foresaw strong resistance to the subsidization of consumption, including social security programs. This opposition would emerge along two main lines. On one hand, critics would argue that subsidizing consumption does not constitute any real form of “enterprise” and therefore lacks economic justification within capitalist logic. On the other side, there is what Kalecki described as a deeply rooted “moral” principle at stake. According to the dominant ethics of capitalism, “You shall earn your bread in sweat”—unless, of course, one has private means (Spencer, 2024, p.6).

Ultimately, this opposition culminates in a rejection of the maintenance of full employment through public intervention. This resistance stems from all the aforementioned reasons, and above all, from the potential social impact that such intervention would have. It challenges the capitalist ideology of “effort,” the presumed efficiency of market mechanisms, and the dominant logic of resource allocation.

2.3. Power spaces distribution

In general terms, the struggle for political power manifests economically through income distribution and politically through the constraints imposed by private capital on governmental policy. Public investment tends to reduce the influence of private capital, while policies aimed at improving workers’ bargaining power diminish profit margins and may erode monopoly power. Consequently, opposition from private interests is not only expected but structurally embedded.

As noted by Arestis and Skuse (2003, p. 27), Kalecki contended that institutional transformation within a developed capitalist framework is a necessary condition for achieving and sustaining full employment. In the absence of such transformation, this objective remains largely unattainable.

However, it is possible to establish a classification of the distribution of these power spaces, based on the income distribution in the private sector (vertical axis),

which is divided between profits and wages, and the orientation of public policies (horizontal axis), which may favor either profits or wages. This orientation is materialized through instruments such as public investment and consumption subsidies. As shown in Table 3, four possible scenarios can be identified based on these combinations⁵, where we assume a wage-led economy.⁶

The upper-left quadrant reflects an economy in which private political power prioritizes profits over wages, signifying that the bargaining power of capital outweighs that of labor. When public policy aligns with this dynamic—through reduced public investment or institutional frameworks that favor capital accumulation—it leads to a profit-driven policy. Conversely, if the state opposes this tendency and promotes real income growth for workers through subsidies or by reinforcing collective bargaining, the economy shifts toward a redistribution-driven strategy, aiming to enhance labor’s role in shaping economic outcomes.

Table 3. Power distribution: developed capitalists’ economies

		Public	
		Profit	Wage
P r i v a t e	P	Profit-driven policy	Redistribution-driven strategy
	W	Government-driven strategy	Wage-driven policy

Source: Own elaboration

On the other hand, a scenario emerges in which private political power, associated with wages, prevails over profits. If the growing bargaining power of workers is supported by policies that expand benefits—assuming these also enhance the government’s political legitimacy—a strategy unfolds in which state authority is reinforced. Conversely, if public policy continues to enhance worker-oriented benefits, a wage-led approach takes shape, where improvements in income and political agency originate from the public sphere.

⁵ This classification is, of course, consistent with the policy analysis of pro-labour and pro-capital distributional strategies proposed by Lavoie and Stockhammer (2013, p. 11), as both approaches are rooted in Kaleckian theory. However, the objective of this exercise is to formally integrate the role of political influence distribution between the private and public sectors.

⁶ See Blecker (1989, p. 395)

In this context, the redistribution strategy creates a setting where private influence over benefits becomes dominant—standing in contrast to a public strategy that aims to rebalance this influence by empowering labor through institutional means.

As previously noted, this political system is based on the assumption of a developed economy, where effective demand operates fully in line with Kaleckian theory. However, Kalecki warns that in underdeveloped economies, structural barriers on the supply side limit the functioning of effective demand. These constraints not only hinder economic dynamism but also result in an unequal distribution of political power among social actors, reinforcing the conditions of underdevelopment. The aim of the following section is to examine how these structural barriers shape both the economic dynamics and the configuration of political power in such contexts.

3. Rethinking the political aspects of development: The Intermediate regimes

The notion of “*intermediate regimes*,” developed by Kalecki, offers a distinctive analytical framework for understanding the political and economic configurations of postcolonial states in the mid-20th century, and it exerted a particularly notable influence on economic thought in India. Unlike traditional development approaches, which often focus narrowly on industrial backwardness or productivity gaps, Kalecki’s concept emphasizes the hybrid and transitional character of these economies.

An *intermediate regime* can be defined as a political and economic configuration of postcolonial states, positioned between capitalist and socialist models. These regimes are characterized by the absence of a consolidated native bourgeoisie, the predominance of foreign capital, a strong state with active economic intervention, and significant political influence of lower or intermediate middle classes. They represent a transitional equilibrium in which external dependence, structural constraints, and internal class dynamics jointly shape both economic development and political orientation (Kalecki, 1967, p. 6). Table 4 integrates the key dimensions of intermediate regimes, providing a structured overview of their political, economic, social, and historical-geopolitical characteristics.

Table 4. Box summarizing: Dimensions of Intermediate regimes	
Dimension	Key aspects
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong state with significant economic intervention. - Political predominance of the lower middle class. - Ideological struggle between alternatives to foreign capitalism and proposals of “state capitalism.” - Non-aligned position in international affairs.
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dependence on foreign capital. - Absence of a consolidated native bourgeoisie. - Limited productive capacity due to structural constraints (e.g., agriculture). - Public investment needed to absorb structural unemployment.
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dominance of intermediate classes: small proprietors, self-employed, rural middle strata. - Lower middle class numerically significant but loosely defined. - Interests situated between traditional elites and lower classes.
Historical-Geopolitical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emergence during decolonization processes. - Positioned between capitalism and socialism. - Domestic development influenced by international dynamics.
Source: Based on Kalecki (1967), Raj (1973) and Skouras (1978)	

Socially, they reflected the interests of intermediate classes—such as wealthier peasants or rural middle strata—positioned between the propertied elites and the lower classes. According to Kalecki, such regimes emerged where there was no fully developed native bourgeoisie and where feudal classes were either weak or politically ineffective. This created conditions for strong state intervention without a definitive ideological break (Skouras, 1978, p. 631).

Notably, these regimes adopted a non-aligned position in the international sphere, further underscoring their intermediate status within the global order. This aspect was by no means secondary, as Kalecki viewed the external sector as a fundamental component of the economic dynamics in such economies. Over time, many of these countries would come to be classified as underdeveloped; however, Kalecki’s framework provides a more nuanced understanding of their historical development. At this stage, he identifies the predominance of foreign capital, establishing a political dichotomy with national capitalism.

Kalecki observed that the apparent absence of a consolidated and influential capitalist class with entrenched political power presented an opportunity for the emergence of a lower middle class capable of taking political control. The intermediate nature of these economies, in fact, marked a political struggle within the ideological arena, reflected in intellectual discourse. This struggle centered around the pursuit of an

alternative model—what Kalecki termed "state capitalism"—a reality that existed between the conflicting political interests of the post-World War II period (Plehwe, 2008, p. 238).

Moreover, it is worth highlighting the emphasis placed on the so-called "lower middle class." Without delving into the possible ideological or cultural motivations behind the use of this term, a defining feature of this intermediate category is the absence of a clear definition or classification, despite its numerical predominance. According to Raj (1973, p. 1189), the class Kalecki refers to includes small proprietors in sectors such as agriculture, industry, and commerce, as well as a variety of self-employed individuals, those who derive income from property generated in combination with their own labor. However, this income is not significantly greater than what they earn from their labor alone, which justifies their inclusion in this group.

Given the political, social, and economic underpinnings of these intermediate regimes, Kalecki's argument focuses on the structural conditions that enable the lower middle class to retain political power, which in turn requires achieving genuine political emancipation. In this context, Kalecki emphasizes that full emancipation necessitates economic independence, particularly through the severance of dependency on foreign capital. This process must be accompanied by agrarian reform—consistent with his view that supply-side constraints contribute to inflationary pressures—and culminate in sustained economic growth, securing both economic and political stability.

The reduction of foreign capital's influence may generate tensions with sectors of national capital. In this regard, it becomes essential to clearly define the responsibilities and boundaries of domestic actors—particularly the lower middle class—to prevent their subordination to the interests of large-scale capital, whether national or foreign in origin.

This issue is especially relevant in the context of developing economies, which are marked by a chronic need for investment. When considering both the political and economic influence of foreign capital alongside persistent investment gaps, it becomes evident that such capital does not address the need for productive expansion or the strengthening of domestic demand. As a result, it may perpetuate a cycle that hinders the effectiveness of aggregate demand and deepens structural unemployment. These conditions reinforce an asymmetrical distribution of political power, consistent with the conflictual dynamics identified by Kalecki.

Within this framework, developing economies operate under a specific form of "full employment," which differs significantly from that observed in advanced capitalist economies. In this context, it is precisely the persistence of this precarious "full employment"—characterized by high levels of informality and underemployment—that enables foreign capital to maintain its control over domestic economic dynamics, thereby exacerbating structural constraints rather than resolving them.

Kalecki identifies the solution in a symbiotic relationship between the lower middle class in power and a state committed to addressing the additional investment needs of underdeveloped economies. This model of state capitalism, centered on coordinated investment, bears a close resemblance to the socialism of the period.

As external capital loses influence, domestic capital emerges as a competing force. Kalecki frames this dynamic as part of a broader ideological contest, wherein underdeveloped economies become arenas of geopolitical rivalry.

In short, an intermediate regime is the rule of the lower-middle class through its control of the State machinery: control that became possible because of the economic weakness of the traditional ruling classes and which is used both to weaken these classes even further and to keep the working class and the rural proletariat politically unorganized and ineffectual. An illustrative exercise applying these reflections was carried out by Kalecki and Kula (1970) for the case of Bolivia, examining its class structure at a time when the state took the reins of the economy.

In this sense, the analysis focuses on the relationship between public and private power, as shown in Table 5, with income distribution reflected in bargaining power. Specifically, the influence of domestic and foreign capital is determined by the degree of monopoly. This approach draws on Kalecki's policy-oriented ideas on economic development, which aim to provide actionable recommendations to improve both the rate and structure of growth, fully incorporating the limiting effects of structural constraints and their emergence (McFarlane, 1996, p. 187).

First, in the upper-left quadrant, we observe a scenario in which a domestic capitalist class holds the bargaining power. In this context, public policy tends to favor the concentration of profits through regulatory frameworks or restrictions on public investment, granting this group greater influence and increasing vulnerability to their investment decisions. Consequently, economic policy is primarily oriented toward protecting domestic profits. An illustrative example of nationalist policies favoring the interests of a domestic business class can be seen in the ultra-nationalistic "America First" doctrine, as noted by Saliya (2025, p. 3).

However, if public policy in this same scenario promotes the attraction of foreign capital, the strategy shifts toward diversifying the sources of economic power, thereby redistributing the influence of profits over wages. Such policies are closely related to the transition toward neoliberalism in Latin America during the 1980s and 1990s, when the domestic business class began a period of political weakening due to the penetration of external capitalism (Walton, 2004). Finally, when public policy aims to strengthen workers' bargaining power through redistributive measures, the scenario becomes more favorable to wages, even within a context dominated by domestic capital. This has been the case in recent years in the Mexican and Brazilian economies, with the strengthening of the minimum wage (Sotomayor, 2021, p. 2; Campos-Vazquez and Esquivel, 2023, p. 360).

Table 5. Power distribution: Intermediate regimes

		Public		Wage
		Profit		
		Intern	Extern	
P r i v a t e	I n t e r n	Domestic profit-driven policy	External-Profit strategy	Redistribution-driven strategy
	E x t e r n	Internal-Profit strategy	Foreign Profit-driven policy	
	W a g e	Government-driven strategy	Private-driven strategy	Wage-driven policy

Source: Own elaboration

Secondly, when external profits dominate and public policy seeks to expand space for domestic gains, a strategy emerges aimed at aligning the political sphere with domestic capitalists. Ultimately, this leads to a policy orientation where the state prioritizes the enhancement of internal profits—particularly in line with the dynamics of state capitalism, which channels investment toward expanding the country's productive potential without posing a threat to small firms.

This approach proves especially advantageous, as the rapid growth of state enterprises creates executive and technical opportunities for ambitious young members of the ruling class. Conversely, scenarios in which the political dominance of foreign capital prevails may compromise the political and economic emancipation of these regimes, by fostering strategies that reinforce the participation and influence of external profits.

3.1. A roadmap for operationalization

As shown in Table 1, Kalecki's state capitalism is key to overcoming structural barriers that limit effective demand in developing economies. Public investment substitutes for inadequate foreign capital, while the state creates productive capacity and regulates external investment to support domestic goals. Investment strategies must also

promote agricultural expansion, making agrarian reform central. Beyond its economic role, the state shapes power relations among social and economic groups, influencing the development process.

It is also relevant to consider contemporary challenges, such as the political coalitions emerging during green transitions and the accompanying economic structural reconfigurations, as explored by Alatorre et al. (2024) and Grazini et al. (2024). These processes involve political constraints that interact with fiscal, monetary, and exchange-rate policies. In this regard, Table 4 integrates political constraints within the Kaleckian framework by considering the private, public, and external sectors, consistent with Neo-Kaleckian wage- and profit-led models (Nofal, 2021).

From a methodological standpoint, the operationalization of this framework requires analyzing the interactions among the three key sectors—private, public, and external—while assessing how policy instruments influence the distribution of political power. These interactions can be evaluated through sectoral participation in investment and other public or institutional dimensions that shape development outcomes. Quantitative approaches, such as power-law distributions and related techniques, provide a rigorous means of capturing these dynamics (Clauset et al., 2009; Virkar, 2012).

Additionally, alternative approaches address the structural vulnerability to which some developing economies are exposed. For instance, Guillaumont's (2014) proposal of an Economic Vulnerability Index (EVI) offers a useful tool for international development policy, consistent with the core theoretical inspiration of this framework—namely, the influence of political dynamics and power relations within the broader landscape of economic interests.

4. Conclusions

In developing economies, the main obstacles to growth stem from structural supply-side constraints. These include, for example, limited agricultural capacity and capacity constraints in key productive sectors, which restrict the economy's ability to respond to increases in demand. Crucially, this does not imply that these economies follow a supply-led growth model. On the contrary, Kalecki implicitly argued that effective demand remains a necessary condition for development—yet one that cannot function fully unless these structural constraints are addressed.

Thus, the central economic concern is not the availability of financial resources in a narrow monetary sense, but rather the potential inflationary pressures that may result from increasing investment in a rigid productive structure. For instance, expanding investment in the absence of a corresponding increase in food supply may reduce real wages and spark an inflationary wage–price spiral.

At the core of the problem lies a distributive dilemma: deciding which social groups will bear the costs of the capital accumulation required to reduce chronic

unemployment. For Kalecki, this dilemma is both political and economic, and it underscores the broader challenge of promoting development in economies marked by deep structural limitations.

This supply-side bottleneck reflects a broader structural duality in developing economies: a demand-driven industrial sector coexists with a rigid, supply-constrained agricultural sector. While industry requires sustained investment to expand capacity and absorb surplus labor, agriculture struggles to meet rising demand due to its semi-feudal organization and limited responsiveness.

For Kalecki, this imbalance is not only economic but political. If demand outpaces agricultural supply, inflation may erode real wages and trigger regressive income redistribution. Thus, development requires aligning economic expansion with the productive capacity of agriculture to avoid deepening structural inequalities.

In his analysis, Kalecki (1976, p.98) stresses that development must be guided by principles of social justice—avoiding inflationary price increases for essential goods and preventing tax burdens on low-income groups. The originality of his approach lies in the priorities it sets, which differ notably from those outlined in early structuralist perspectives. Rather than viewing development as a purely technical process of capital accumulation or labor absorption, Kalecki emphasizes its inherently social and political nature.

In this sense, his vision resonates strongly with the political and distributive concerns later emphasized by Latin American structuralism. This convergence opens the door to a fruitful and intense dialogue between Kalecki and the pioneers of structuralist thought in the region, such as Prebisch and Furtado, giving rise to what may be termed a Kaleckian–structuralist perspective. Instead of focusing solely on the expansion of the industrial or capitalist sector, this framework highlights the importance of equitable growth through the strengthening of non-capitalist sectors—particularly agriculture and rural areas—as a means to expand internal demand and foster a more balanced path of structural transformation.

As with investment, the concept of full employment differs between developed and developing economies. In developed economies, Kalecki emphasized investment as the key driver of the business cycle. When aggregate demand fails to absorb the available labor supply, full employment becomes unattainable. This structural feature of capitalism explains why unemployment can persist.

Achieving full employment requires sufficient productive capacity and sustained support from the components of effective demand. However, this goal is not only a technical or economic challenge—it also faces political constraints. Historically, capitalism has avoided prolonged periods of full employment, as such periods often provoke significant social and political change.

Moreover, maintaining full employment through state intervention is technically feasible. Increased production and employment benefit both workers and entrepreneurs, as profits generally rise alongside wages. These policies can be designed to avoid tax increases that would erode business profits, thus maintaining a balance between economic efficiency and political acceptability. The resistance to such measures arises from the fact that sustained full employment diminishes the level of control capital holds over the workforce.

The struggle for political power is reflected in income distribution and the constraints private capital imposes on government policy. Public investment weakens private capital's influence, while policies that enhance workers' bargaining power reduce profit margins and diminish monopoly power. As a result, opposition from private interests is both expected and structurally ingrained. In this framework, the redistribution strategy shifts power toward private control over benefits, while a public strategy aims to counterbalance this by empowering labor through institutional mechanisms.

Kalecki's theory assumes that effective demand operates fully in developed economies, but in developing economies, structural supply-side constraints limit its functioning. These constraints not only hinder economic dynamism but also reinforce unequal political power, perpetuating underdevelopment.

In this regard, he introduces the concept of intermediate regimes, where the lower middle class must retain political power through economic independence. Achieving this requires reducing reliance on foreign capital and implementing agrarian reform to address supply-side limitations.

Reducing foreign capital's influence may provoke tensions with domestic capital. To prevent subordination to large-scale capital, it is essential to define the roles of domestic actors, particularly the lower middle class.

This is crucial for developing economies facing chronic investment gaps. Foreign capital does not address the need for productive expansion or boost domestic demand. Instead, it reinforces a cycle of limited aggregate demand and deepens structural unemployment, exacerbating an unequal distribution of political power, as Kalecki highlighted.

To overcome these limitations, Kalecki emphasizes the importance of state capitalism in developing economies. Public investment plays a crucial role in displacing foreign investment that fails to generate sufficient capacity to absorb structural unemployment. The state must not only create this capacity but also establish a regulatory framework that ensures foreign investment aligns with domestic development goals.

Furthermore, any investment strategy, whether public or private, must be paired with a sustained increase in agricultural production, necessitating agrarian reform. This

makes agrarian reform a key component of a broader development agenda. In this framework, the state is not only an economic actor but also a political one, shaping power dynamics through its policies. The stance the state adopts towards various social and economic groups influences the balance of power and the overall development trajectory.

References

ALATORRE, J. E.; JUAREZ, J.; MORENO-BRID, J. C.; PORCILE, G. Political conflict, green capabilities, and growth patterns in a Kaleckian small open economy. *Green Capabilities, and Growth Patterns in a Kaleckian Small Open Economy*, 18 Dec. 2024.

ARNDT, H. W. 'Full employment' in historical perspective. *Australian Quarterly*, v. 66, n. 2, p. 1–12, 1994.

ARESTIS, P.; SKUSE, F. The relevance of Kalecki's 'Political Aspects of Full Employment' to the twenty-first century. In: ARESTIS, P.; SAWYER, M. (eds.). *Kalecki's Economics Today*. London: Routledge, 2003. p. 27-43.

BAÑBURA, M.; BOBEICA, E.; MARTÍNEZ HERNÁNDEZ, C. *What drives core inflation? The role of supply shocks*. Frankfurt am Main: European Central Bank, 2023. (ECB Working Paper, n. 2875).

BIELSCHOWSKY, R. Evolución de las Ideas de la CEPAL. *Revista de la CEPAL*, edición especial, oct. 1998.

BLECKER, R. A. International competition, income distribution and economic growth. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, v. 13, n. 3, p. 395-412, 1989.

BRESSER-PEREIRA, L. C. Method and passion in Celso Furtado. In: CALDENTEY, E. P.; VERNENGO, M. (ed.). *Ideas, Policies and Economic Development in the Americas*. London: Routledge, 2007. p.27-48.

CAMPOS-VAZQUEZ, R. M.; ESQUIVEL, G. The effect of the minimum wage on poverty: Evidence from a quasi-experiment in Mexico. *The Journal of Development Studies*, v. 59, n. 3, p. 360–380, 2023.

CHAKRABARTI, S. Agriculture-industry linkage: The problems of effective demand and supply constraint. *Review of Development and Change*, v. 8, n. 2, p. 145–170, 2003.

CHAKRABARTI, S. A macroeconomic structure of employment: rural-urban conflict in a Kaleckian framework. *Review of Radical Political Economics*, v. 43, n. 2, p. 172–197, 2011.

CHAKRABARTI, S. Interrogating inclusive growth: formal-informal duality, complementarity, conflict. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, v. 37, n. 6, p. 1349–1379, 2013.

CLAUSET, A.; SHALIZI, C. R.; NEWMAN, M. E. Power-law distributions in empirical data. *SIAM Review*, v. 51, n. 4, p. 661–703, 2009.

CYPHER, J. M. The origins of developmentalist theory: The empirically based, historically contextualized political economy of Furtado. *International Journal of Political Economy*, v. 43, n. 4, p. 15-32, 2014.

FITZGERALD, E. V. K. Kalecki on planned growth in the mixed economy. *Development and Change*, v. 19, n. 1, p. 33–52, 1988.

FITZGERALD, E. V. K. Kalecki on financing development: an approach to the macroeconomics of the semi-industrialised economy. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, v. 14, n. 2, p. 183–203, 1990.

GHOSH, J. Michal Kalecki and the economics of development. In: JOMO, K. S. (ed.). *The Pioneers of Development Economics: Great Economists on Development*. London: Zed Books, 2005. p. 109-122.

GRAZINI, C.; GUARINI, G.; PORCILE, J. G. Institutional change and ecological structural change. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, v. 71, p. 354–368, 2024.

GUILLAUMONT, P. An economic vulnerability index: its design and use for international development policy. In: GUILLAUMONT, P. *Measuring Vulnerability in Developing Countries*. London; New York: Routledge, 2014. p. 11–46.

GUIZZO, D.; ALMEIDA, F.; BRITES, M.; DE PAULA, L. G. From periphery to core? Mapping a history of Post-Keynesian economics in Brazil. *Review of Political Economy*, p. 1-24, 2024.

JEFFERSON, T.; KING, J. E. Michal Kalecki and critical realism. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, v. 35, n. 5, p. 957–972, 2011.

JUAREZ, J. La influencia de Kalecki en el pensamiento estructuralista de América Latina. *Revista de Economía Crítica*, v. 40, 2025.

JUÁREZ, J.; MORENO-BRID, J. C. *Kaleckian insights on structural heterogeneity*. *Revista Economía e Políticas Públicas*, v. 12, n. 1, p. 1–11, 2024.

KALECKI, M. Political aspects of full employment. *The Political Quarterly*, v. 14, n. 4, p. 322-330, 1943.

KALECKI, M. Three ways to full employment. In: *The Economics of Full Employment*. London: Oxford University Press, 1944. p. 39.

KALECKI, M. The problem of financing of economic development. *Indian Economic Review*, v. 2, n. 3, p. 1-22, 1955.

KALECKI, M. Some remarks on the socio-economic aspects of intermediate systems. *Polish Round Table*, v. 1, p. 97, 1967.

KALECKI, M. The problem of financing economic development in a mixed economy. In: KALECKI, M. (ed.). *Essays on Developing Economies*. Hassocks: Harvester Press, 1976.

KALECKI, M.; KULA, M. Notas sobre los aspectos sociales y económicos de los "Regímenes intermedios": El caso de Bolivia. *Estudios Internacionales*, v. 4, n. 15, p. 84–96, 1970.

LAVOIE, M.; STOCKHAMMER, E. Wage-led growth: concept, theories and policies. In: LAVOIE, M.; STOCKHAMMER, E. (eds.). *Wage-led Growth: An Equitable Strategy for Economic Recovery*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2013. p. 13-39.

LEWIS, A. Economic development with unlimited supplies of labour. *The Manchester School*, v. 22, p. 139-191, 1954.

LÓPEZ, J. G.; ASSOUS, M. Michal Kalecki: a pioneer of development economics. In: LÓPEZ, J. G.; ASSOUS, M. (eds.). *Michal Kalecki*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010. p. 174-191.

MARSH, J.; SHARPE, T.; PHILP, B. Achieving full employment: History, theory, and policy. In: BRESSER-PEREIRA, L. C.; MARSH, J.; HARVEY, P. (Org.). *The Routledge Handbook of Heterodox Economics*. London: Routledge, 2017. p. 488–498.

McCARTNEY, M.; HARRISS-WHITE, B. The intermediate regime and intermediate classes revisited: a critical political economy of Indian economic development from 1980 to Hindutva. *Queen Elizabeth House Working Paper Series*, n. 45, 2000.

McFARLANE, B. Michal Kalecki and the political economy of the Third World. In: KING, J.E. (ed.). *An Alternative Macroeconomic Theory: The Kaleckian Model and Post-Keynesian Economics*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 1996. p. 187-218.

NOFAL, S. An assessment of the debates over income distribution and growth in the Neo-Kaleckian literature. *Brazilian Journal of Political Economy*, v. 41, n. 4, p. 782–796, 2021.

NURKSE, R. Problems of capital formation in underdeveloped countries. Oxford: Blackwell, 1955.

ORSOLIN-TEIXEIRA, F.; CORONEL, D. A.; OREIRO, J. L. Income distribution and development: Celso Furtado's theory in a context of global economic changes and its proximity to neo (post)-Kaleckian literature. *PSL Quarterly Review*, v. 76, n. 307, p. 337-351, 2023.

PEREZ CALDENTEY, E. P.; VERNENGO, M. Introduction: Ideas, policies and economic development in the Americas. In: CALDENTEY, E. P.; VERNENGO, M. (eds.). *Ideas, Policies and Economic Development in the Americas*. London: Routledge, 2007. p. 19-26.

PORCILE, G. Latin-American structuralism and neo-structuralism. In: STIRATI, A.; MELONI, W.; RODRIGUEZ, O. (eds.). *New Perspectives on Structural Change: Causes and Consequences of Structural Change in the Global Economy*. London: Routledge, 2021. p. 50-71.

PLEHWE, D. The origins of the neoliberal economic development discourse. In: MIROWSKI, P.; PLEHWE, D. (eds.). *The Road from Mont Pèlerin: The Making of the Neoliberal Thought Collective*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2009. p. 238-279.

RAJ, K. N. The politics and economics of "intermediate regimes". *Economic and Political Weekly*, v. 8, n. 25, p. 1189-1198, 1973.

ROCHON, L. P.; CZACHOR, M.; BACHUREWICZ, G. Introduction: Kalecki and Kaleckian Economics. *Review of Political Economy*, v. 32, n. 4, p. 487-491, 2020.

ROWTHORN, B. The political economy of full employment in modern Britain. *Centre for Economic Performance*, London School of Economics and Political Science, Discussion Paper n. 432, 1999.

SACHS, I. Kalecki and development planning. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics & Statistics*, v. 39, n. 1, p. 1-8, 1977.

SACHS, I. Learning political economy with Michal Kalecki. *Review of Political Economy*, v. 11, n. 3, p. 267-272, 1999.

SALIYA, C. A. *Donald Trump's Ultra-Nationalistic Policies: An Era of*. Available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5114764

SÁNCHEZ-ANCOCHEA, D. Anglo-Saxon versus Latin American structuralism in development economics. In: CALDENTEY, E. P.; VERNENGO, M. (eds.). *Ideas, Policies and Economic Development in the Americas*. London: Routledge, 2007. p. 226-244.

SAWYER, M. The economics of Michał Kalecki. *Eastern European Economics*, v. 23, n. 3, p. 5-39, 1985.

SAWYER, M. Political aspects of full employment: eight decades on. *Review of Political Economy*, v. 35, n. 4, p. 1109–1123, 2023.

SETTERFIELD, M. *Inflation and distribution during the post-COVID recovery: a Kaleckian approach*. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, v. 46, n. 4, p. 587–611, 2023.

SKOURAS, T. The “intermediate regime” and industrialization prospects. *Development and Change*, v. 9, n. 4, p. 631–648, 1978.

SOTOMAYOR, O. J. Can the minimum wage reduce poverty and inequality in the developing world? Evidence from Brazil. *World Development*, v. 138, p. 105182, 2021.

SPENCER, D. A. Beyond full employment: Keynes and Kalecki on our economic future. *Review of Political Economy*, [S. l.], 26 feb. 2024.

SUNKEL, O. *La inflación chilena: un enfoque heterodoxo*. *El Trimestre Económico*, v. 63, n. 249(1), p. 319–351, 1996.

TOPOROWSKI, J. Political aspects of full employment in retrospect. *Contributions to Political Economy*, v. 42, n. 1, p. 226-241, 2023.

VIRKAR, Y. S. *Power-law distributions and binned empirical data*. 2012. Master's thesis, University of Colorado at Boulder.

WALTON, M. Neoliberalism in Latin America: Good, bad, or incomplete? *Latin American Research Review*, v. 39, n. 3, p. 165–184, 2004.